

**READING INTERVENTION PROGRAM FOR STRUGGLING
READERS IN QUITERIO SAN JOSE ELEMENTARY
SCHOOL, DISTRICT OF TERESA**

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Reading Intervention Program for Struggling Readers in Quiterio San Jose Elementary School, District of Teresa

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of reading intervention program for struggling readers in Quiterio San Jose Elementary School, District of Teresa. The respondents of the study were the one hundred percent total population of Grade Five pupils. This consists of 247 pupils during the administration of pretest in Phil-IRI. After the administration of the pretest the result was evaluated. A researcher-made questionnaire-checklist, pretest and posttests were utilized to determine the reading skills performance level of the respondents with respect to word recognition, vocabulary development, listening skills and comprehension skills before and after exposure to reading intervention program with respect to the aspects mentioned above. The study found out that majority of the pupils are normal when it comes to nutritional status. For pupils' reading materials available at home, all have books while more than half have encyclopedia or dictionary and one third has magazines and journals. The study revealed also that there was a gain in the reading skills performance level of pupils with respect to word recognition, vocabulary development, listening skills and comprehension skills after exposure to reading intervention program. The study concluded that there is a significant difference in the reading performance of the pupils after the intervention program with respect to word recognition, vocabulary development, listening skills and comprehension skills when grouped by reading level, sex, nutritional status. Pupils' reading materials available at home are not predictors of the reading level of the pupils.

Keywords: *reading, Phil-IRI, struggling reader*

Introduction

Reading is the cornerstone of an effective education. Without this skill we are limited in so many important life activities: we cannot understand a newspaper, read directions of a new recipe, enjoy a favorite novel, or read a prescription bottle of medication.

One of the major goals of the Philippine Education system specifically of the Department of Education (DepEd) is to make every Filipino Child a successful reader at his appropriate level by the end of Grade Three.

Anent to this, the Department of Education enforced the policy "Every Child a Reader". In this program, it is expected that no pupil will be promoted to the next higher grade unless literacy skills in a particular grade level have been developed. All possible means of assistance and encouragement shall be extended to enable the child to read. The cited memorandum reiterates very school to implement reading intervention program to improve the reading proficiency of pupils.

Intervention program for students with difficulties in reading tend to focus early on the development of decoding skills followed by fluency building in connected texts. More specifically and important for the present review, building reading fluency interventions have often featured repeated reading activities aimed at improving the speed and accuracy of students' text reading. Repeated reading offers students an opportunity to read and reread the same text multiple times and is implemented in a variety of formats including partner reading, reading to an older peer or family member, or reading with an audiotape.

For students with or at risk for learning disabilities, developing fluency with reading connected texts remains a formidable challenge. In response, teachers often use repeated reading practices designed to provide students with multiple exposures to the same words.

The researcher, as a grade five teacher for almost six years has observed that most of the weaknesses of pupils who struggle in reading were word recognition and vocabulary which have made their poorer reading performance that affects fluency in reading. In view of this the researcher was prompted to conduct this study to determine the effectiveness of reading intervention program on the reading fluency of pupils.

Research Questions

This study aimed determine the effectiveness of Reading Intervention Program for Struggling Readers in Quiterio San Jose Elementary School, District of Teresa. Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions.

1. What is the profile of the grade five struggling readers in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. nutritional status; and
 - 1.3. pupils' reading materials available at home?
2. What is the reading skills performance level of the respondents before and after exposure Repeated Reading Intervention Program with respect to:
 - 2.1. word recognition;

- 2.2. vocabulary development;
- 2.3. listening skills; and
- 2.4. comprehension skills
3. Is there a significant difference on the reading skills performance level of the respondents before and after exposure to repeated reading interventions with respect to above-mentioned areas?
4. Is there a significant difference on the reading performance level of the pupils after exposure to reading intervention program in terms of their profile?

Literature Review

Ozdemir (2010) stressed that reading is fundamental in getting knowledge as all lessons and learning activities are mostly based on the power of comprehensive reading; indeed, it is really necessary to read comprehensively. Also, reading comprehensively really affects a learner's education and his life as a whole. Learning in any lesson depends on understanding of the learning instrument of the lesson; thus, learner who cannot read comprehensively finds it difficult for him/her to be successful in his/her lessons.

Likewise, Julian (2005) stated that reading comprehension is a complex process which involves meaning and understanding. If a reader comprehends a written text, he must know what the text means and he must be able to understand what is written. It also involves the knowledge with logical ordering of instructional elements in reading a text.

Moreover, Paloma (2005) stressed that the skills of reading, thinking and comprehension are closely tied together, and are the most basic building blocks for success in school and throughout life. To help the pupils master these skills, the reading teacher must read aloud to preschoolers to appreciate reading books at an early age and make it easy for the children to read books.

Meanwhile, Hollowel (2009) stated that reading intervention programs are crucial in helping struggling students become successful readers. Teacher should ideally have at least two intervention programs available to the use with small groups or individual students. Programs that are research-based are the most effective because they have been designed for students to learn, practice, and reinforce essential reading skills.

As stressed by Hangen-McLaine, Hohit and Hamey (2007) there is a need for a contemporary sight words-based reading program that built a base of high frequency words for students and then used those words to teach basic phonemic patterns and decoding strategies. This led to the creation of PCI Reading Program, a comprehensive leveled program for non-readers of all ages. Like other effective sight-words based programs, the PCI Reading Program begins with effortless discrimination and mastery-based learning at a list of words.

In this connection, Carlisle (2004) explains the teacher's possible options in teaching struggling readers which includes fostering incidental word games another is providing vocabulary instructions which includes pre-reading study of critical vocabulary, linking vocabulary to domain knowledge and learning dictionary skills and the last is teaching and encouraging the use of strategies to derive the meaning of unfamiliar words in texts.

Furthermore, Jordan (2007) made a study on the utilization of instructional materials in teaching elementary reading. The result showed that the adequacy of instructional materials in reading is adequate. On the extent of utilization of instructional materials in developing word recognition is utilized. On the comprehension skills, instructional materials with respect to noting details is utilized, sequencing events, utilized, cause and effect, utilized, following directions, utilized: and predicting outcomes, utilized. The study concluded that there is significant difference on the utilization of instructional materials and seminars attended and the length of service of teachers.

Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive method of investigation then was applied to assess the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, nutritional status and pupils' reading materials available at home. This method was also utilized to determine the reading performance of the respondents with respect to word recognition, vocabulary development, listening skills and comprehension skills. Much more, the results of the findings presented the significant difference on the reading skills performance level of the respondents before and after exposure to reading intervention program with respects to the aspects mentioned above.

Respondents

The researcher used the one hundred percent of the total population of Grade Five pupils of QSJES. This consists of 247 pupils during the administration of pretest in Phil-IRI. After administration of the pretest the result was evaluated. The 122 pupils who failed or marked as struggling readers were exposed to the intervention program which is repeated reading intervention to determine the effectiveness of the reading intervention program. After the exposure to the intervention program the posttest was given.

Instrument

In conducting this study, the researcher used questionnaire consisting of two parts. Part I was the documentary analysis about the

respondents' profile in terms of sex, nutritional status and pupils' reading materials available at home.

Part II was the pretest and posttest using the modified Phi-IRI oral tests in reading skills for Grade V pupils, which is the main instrument of gathering data. This part of the questionnaire tested the reading performance of the respondents with seven (7) items for every aspect namely: word recognition, vocabulary development, listening skills and comprehension skills. Pretest and posttest contained the same content to determine the reading performance of the struggling readers after being exposed to the repeated reading intervention program.

Procedure

As preliminary step, the researcher prepared a GANTT Chart of Activities to be guided of the step-by-step procedures in conducting the study. A letter was sent to the Division Superintendent of the Schools, Division of Rizal, and request permission to conduct the study using the grade five struggling readers in Quiterio San Jose Elementary School Teresa, Rizal as the respondents. When the permission is already approved, the researcher waited for the results of the pretest to determine the struggling readers who would undergo the Repeated Reading Intervention Program. The Reading Skills Test Items were recorded one by one to facilitate the administration of the test and to avoid discrepancies in the testing. Equal treatment on administering the test was given.

The responses will be checked applying statistical treatment appropriate to answer the problems stated in chapter 1. Summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations were formulated. Revision of the manuscript was based on the recommendations given during the final oral defense.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Profile of the Grade Five Struggling Readers in Terms of Sex, Nutritional Status, and Pupils' Reading Materials Available at Home

Table 1. *Profile of the Pupils*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Reading Level			
Male	63	51.6	1
Female	59	48.4	2
Total	122	100.0	
Nutritional Status			
Severely Wasted	7	5.7	3
Wasted	14	11.5	2
Normal	97	79.5	1
Over Weight	3	2.5	4
Obese	1	0.8	5
Total	122	100.0	
Types of Reading Materials			
Books	122	100.0	1
Newspaper	58	47.5	3
Magazines	55	45.1	4
Journals	24	19.7	5
Encyclopedia/Dictionary	66	54.1	2

It is indicated in the table that the male struggling readers exceeded the females by 4 with 63 out of 122 or 51.6% male. The remaining 59 are female. For the nutritional status of the pupils, majority of the pupils at 79.5% have normal nutritional status. Out of the 122 pupils, 14 or 11.5 % are wasted and 7 or 5.7% are severely wasted. There are also pupils who are either overweight or obese. They compose the remaining 3.3%.

On the reading materials available, 100% of the pupils have books. Second in rank are the 54.1% with encyclopedia or dictionary. Third in rank are the 47.5% with newspaper as one of available reading materials. Magazines and journal are also available to 45.1% and 19.7% respectively. There are multiple answers with some pupils having all the reading materials at home.

Reading Performance Level of the Respondents Before and After Exposure on the Reading Intervention Program with Respect to Word Recognition, Vocabulary Development, Listening Skills and Comprehension Skills

Before the intervention program, majority of the pupils has 8 or more miscues, they are the 60.7% who are in the frustration level. Second in rank are the pupils with 3-7 miscues which compromise 36.1%. Only 4 out of the 122 struggling reading have less than 3 miscues. Highest number of miscues observed was 13 and 1 is the lowest. The mean number of miscues is 7.37.

After the intervention program, no pupil was left in the frustration level with 7 as the greatest number of miscues. Mean number of miscues was 5.6. Majority of the pupils at 97.5% are in the instructional level having 3 – 7 miscues. Only 3 out of the 122 reached the

independent level.

Table 2. *Reading Performance Level in Word Recognition of the Pupils Before and After Exposure to Reading Intervention Program*

Miscues		Pretest			Posttest		
No. of Miscues	Reading Level	F	%	Rank	F	%	Rank
0-2	Independent	4	3.3	3	3	2.5	2
3-7	Instructional	44	36.1	2	119	97.5	1
8 above	Frustration	75	60.7	1	-	-	.
Total		122	100.0		122	100.0	
Lowest Number of Miscues Observed				1			
Highest Number of Miscues Observed				13	7		
Mean				7.4	5.6		
Standard Dev.				2.72	2.36		

Findings imply that after exposure to intervention program the number of miscues is significantly lower in the posttest. The study on hand is related to the study of Therrein (2004) that repeated readings enhance fluency and comprehension for both normally achieving students and those with learning disabilities.

Table 3. *Reading Performance Level in Vocabulary Development of the Pupils Before and After Exposure to Reading Intervention Program*

Reading Level		Pretest			Posttest		
Score	F	%	Rank	F	%	Rank	
6-7	52	42.6	2	68	55.7	1	
5	15	12.3	3	35	28.7	2	
4 Below	55	45.1	1	19	15.6	3	
Total		122	100.0		122	100.0	
Highest Score		7		7			
Lowest Score		0		0			
Mean		4.86		5.57			
Standard Dev.		2.20		2.36			
Mean Percentage Score		69.43		79.57			

Before exposure to the reading intervention program, there are more pupils in the frustration level in reading performance level in vocabulary development. This comprise of 55 pupils or 45.1%. On the other hand, 52 or 42.6% of the pupils are in the independent level with the remaining 12.3% in the instructional level.

After exposure to the reading intervention program, 68 out of the 122 or 55.7% are already in the independent level, 28.7% in the instructional level while 15.6% remained in the frustration level.

This means that there is a change in the reading level of the pupils though only 1 out of four pupils is still in the frustration level. The percent of skills mastered of MPS rose from 69.43% to 79.57%. This is in conformity with the statement of McNamara (2007) that in order to become a successful reader, a child must be able to decode the individual words on the page and must be able to comprehend the text.

Table 4. *Reading Performance Level in Listening Skills of the Pupils Before and After Exposure to Reading Intervention Program*

Score (level)	Pretest				Posttest		
	Score	F	%	Rank	F	%	Rank
Independent	6-7	4	3.3	3	37	30.1	2
Instructional	5	16	13.1	2	69	56.6	1
Frustration	4 Below	102	83.6	1	16	13.1	3
Total		122	100.0		122	100.0	
Highest Score		7		7			
Lowest Score		0		0			
Mean		3.40		4.49			
Standard Dev.		1.84		2.12			
Mean Percentage Score		48.57		64.14			

With respect to listening skills, majority of the pupils at 102 out of 122 or 83.6% are in the frustration level. After the reading intervention program almost half of the pupils moved up to instructional level. At the beginning only 3.3% are in the independent level, after exposure to the intervention program there was an increase to 30.1%. There was an appreciation of MPS from 48.57 % to 64.14%.

Findings imply that more intervention should be done to improve the listening skills of the pupils. This confirms the findings of Carlisle (2004) explains that the teacher’s possible options in teaching struggling readers are fostering incidental word, learning having lots of talking in the classroom, listening to books read aloud and playing games.

Table 5. Reading Performance Level in Comprehension Skills of the Pupils Before and After Exposure to Reading Intervention Program

Score (level)	Pretest				Posttest			
	Score	F	%	Rank	F	%	Rank	
Independent	6-7	-	-	-	57	46.8	2	
Instructional	5	-	-	-	63	51.6	1	
Frustration	4 Below	122	100.0	1	2	1.6	3	
Total		122	100.0		122	100.0		
Highest Score			4			7		
Lowest Score			0			0		
Mean			2.04			5.57		
Standard Dev.			1.43			2.36		
Mean Percentage Score			29.14			79.57		

For comprehension skills, almost all of the pupils at 100% are in the frustration level. After the intervention program, only 2 out of 122 or 1.6% remained in the frustration level, majority at 51.6% are in the instructional level and 46.8% in the independent level.

Just like in the other skills, the lowest observed score was zero and the highest was a perfect 4 before exposure. After the intervention program, the lowest score observed was 3 and the highest was 7. The MPS stood at 29.14 before exposure and 79.57% after. This means that the intervention made a big difference in the comprehension skills mastered by the pupils. This implies that reading enhancement activities improved the reading comprehension skills of pupils. The study on hand is parallel to the study of Mathus and Lapadat (2006) that reading intervention strategies improve the reading comprehension of pupils.

Significant Difference on the Reading Skills Performance Level of the Respondents Before and After Exposure to Reading Intervention Program with Respect to the Different Aspects

Table 6. Result of the Test on the Significant Difference on the Reading Skills Performance of the Respondents Before and After Exposure to Reading Intervention Program

Aspects	t-value	p-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Word Recognition	-7.490	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Vocabulary Development	1.078	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Listening Skills	10.160	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Comprehension Skills	23.128	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

It can be gleaned from the table that the p-values associated with the computed t-values for word recognition, vocabulary skills, listening skills and comprehension skills are all lower than 0.05. This means that there is no reason to accept the null hypothesis. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in reading performance of the pupils' word recognition, vocabulary development, listening skills and comprehension skills after exposure to the reading intervention program.

The t-value for word recognition is negative, this means that the number of miscues is significantly lower in the posttest. On the other hand, all the other values are positive as the scores of the pupils in vocabulary development, listening skills and comprehension skills are significantly higher after exposure to the reading intervention program.

Findings imply that the reading intervention program is effective even though a lot of work is still needed to convert the big number of pupils in the frustration and instructional to independent level. The study on hand is related to the study of Lyon (2008) revealed the effectiveness of intervention program not only in comprehension skills of the pupils but also on the other reading skills.

Significant Difference in the Reading Performance of the Pupils After Exposure to Reading Intervention Program in Terms of Their Profile

The p-value of 0.006 for vocabulary development when grouped by sex is lower than 0.05. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the vocabulary development in terms of sex. Data showed that the female have higher score than the male pupils. The word recognition, listening skills and comprehension skills of the male and female pupils in the posttest do not differ.

When grouped by nutritional status, it can be seen that the p-values for reading comprehension of 0.019 is the only value lower than 0.05. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected for comprehension skills but the null hypothesis is accepted for word recognition, vocabulary development and listening skills. This means that there is a significant difference in the comprehension skills of the pupils after the intervention program when grouped by nutritional status. On the other hand, the nutritional status has no bearing on the word recognition, vocabulary development and listening skills of the pupils.

The p-values associated with the computed F-values for reading materials available at home are all higher than 0.05. This means that there is no reason to reject the null hypothesis. It is concluded that there is no significant difference in the performance of the pupils in word recognition, vocabulary development, listening skills and comprehension skills after exposure to the intervention program when

grouped by reading materials available at home. Findings imply that the reading materials available at home are not a predictor in the reading level of the pupils. They may be available but if pupils do not read at home or use the available materials then the richness of materials is useless.

Table 7. Result of the Test on the Significant Difference in the Reading Performance of the Pupils After Exposure to Reading Intervention Program

<i>Aspects</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Reading Level				
Word Recognition	0.486	0.487	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Vocabulary Development	7.889	0.006	Reject Ho	Significant
Listening Skills	2.061	0.154	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Comprehension Skills	0.461	0.499	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Nutritional Status				
Word Recognition	0.447	0.775	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Vocabulary Development	1.535	0.197	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Listening Skills	2.405	0.053	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Comprehension Skills	3.028	0.019	Reject Ho	Significant
Reading Materials Available				
Word Recognition	1.874	0.120	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Vocabulary Development	0.287	0.886	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Listening Skills	0.594	0.668	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Comprehension Skills	1.568	0.188	Accept Ho	Not Significant

The study on hand is similar to the findings of Regala (2007) that children from their early childhood should be encouraged to read and love books. When they see adult members of their family holding and reading books, they will imitate them and it will be the start of a worthy leisure time activity.

In terms of sex, findings implied that it is not significant on the reading performance of the Grade V struggling readers. This implies that being male or female has nothing to do with the reading performance of the pupils.

The findings are similarly related to the study of Brantmeier (2004) results revealed that there is no significant difference between males and females in the written recall and multiple choice comprehension scores across passages.

With respect to the pupils' nutritional status, findings imply that there is no significant difference in word recognition, vocabulary development and listening skills when grouped in nutritional status after exposure to reading intervention program. Findings also implied that there is a significant difference in comprehension skills after exposure to the intervention program when group in nutritional status.

The study on hand is related to the study of Kar et al. (2008) that shows nutritional status of the pupils are significantly related to their comprehension skills.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

The reading performance of the pupils in word recognition, vocabulary development, listening skills and comprehension skills are significantly higher after the intervention program.

The reading levels of the male and female pupils with respect to vocabulary development differ. They also differ with respect to comprehension level when grouped by nutritional status. Reading materials available at home are not predictors of the reading level of the pupils.

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